

Effects of Planting Season Shifts on Major insect Pests and virus diseases of Tobacco in Northern Vietnam: A Review

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Abstract

The shift in the tobacco planting season from the traditional planting season (February to early March) to an earlier planting time (December to early January) in the northern mountainous provinces of Vietnam in recent years has substantially changed field ecological conditions, thereby strongly affecting tobacco growth and the occurrence of insect pests and diseases. This review synthesises data from both domestic and international scientific publications, combined with field survey results conducted by the Vietnam Tobacco Institute during the period 2005–2026, to evaluate the effects of planting season shifts on the population dynamics of major tobacco insect pests and diseases.

Previous studies have demonstrated that early planting significantly reduces the incidence and severity of several major insect pests, including tobacco budworm, armyworm, tobacco aphid, and green stink bug, due to lower temperatures and prolonged dry conditions during the stalk and leaf growth stage. However, these environmental conditions may also greatly increase the risk of virus diseases transmitted by insect vectors, particularly *Potato virus Y* (PVY). Early-planted tobacco has slower growth and an extended susceptible period to viral infection and winged aphids, thereby enhancing the role of winged aphids in virus transmission within the field.

Overall, planting season is considered a key ecological factor in integrated pest management (IPM) for tobacco raw material production. A planting time from late January to mid-February is considered to be more suitable under the ecological conditions of northern mountainous regions, as it can reduce the risk of both insect pests and viral diseases while maintaining favourable crop growth, yield, and leaf quality. Nevertheless, further studies are needed to determine the optimal planting time for each ecological region under current climate change conditions.

Keywords: Tobacco; Planting season shift; Potato virus Y; Aphid vectors; Integrated pest management; Northern Vietnam.

1. Introduction

Tobacco is a short-term industrial crop with high economic value and provides greater economic returns than many other crops cultivated in the mountainous provinces of Northern Vietnam, including Lang Son, Bac Kan (current: Thai Nguyen Province), and Cao Bang. Tobacco production not only contributes to improving farmers' income but also supplies an important source of raw tobacco material for the domestic and export tobacco manufacturing industry. Previous studies have shown that tobacco has a growth duration of approximately 90–120 days and grows optimally under temperatures ranging from 22 to 28°C. Plant growth is inhibited at temperatures below 10–13°C, and plants may die when temperatures fall below 2–3°C (Li Y et al., 2021). The harvesting stage requires dry weather conditions with low rainfall to facilitate leaf ripening; excessive rainfall during this period may reduce leaf thickness and leaf weight, prolong the ripening process, and increase difficulties during curing (FAO, 2024). In addition, tobacco grows well in loose loamy soils with good drainage and a low risk of flooding (Srinivasa et al., 2016).

The growth and development of tobacco plants are influenced by numerous biotic and abiotic factors, including climatic conditions, soil characteristics, weeds, insect pests, and diseases. Harmful organisms can occur in both the seedbed and field stages, causing significant damage to plant growth, yield, and tobacco leaf quality. Common diseases in seedbeds include damping-off, target spot, and bacterial angular leaf spot, whereas major pests and diseases in the field include cutworm, tobacco budworm, tobacco aphid, green stink bug, armyworm, frog-eye leaf spot, target spot, brown spot,

black shank, bacterial wilt, hollow stalk rot, and several viral diseases such as *Tobacco mosaic virus* (TMV), *Cucumber mosaic virus* (CMV), *Tobacco leaf curl virus* (TLCV), *Potato virus Y* (PVY), *Tomato necrotic ringspot virus* (TNRV), and *Tomato spotted wilt virus* (TSWV). According to Daniel Abebe (2024), insect pests may cause approximately 34% reduction in cured leaf yield if appropriate management measures are not implemented.

Among some cultivation practices, in addition to cultivar, soil conditions, irrigation, and fertiliser, planting time is one of the most important factors affecting tobacco growth and the population dynamics of insect pests and diseases. Previous studies have demonstrated that appropriate adjustment of planting time can improve yield and leaf quality while reducing insect pest and disease pressure in the field (Ali Shahzad et al., 2014). To effectively manage harmful organisms, integrated pest management (IPM) plays an important role through the integration of various agronomic and ecological measures aimed at maintaining pest populations below the economic threshold and reducing dependence on chemical pesticides (Tobacco Production Guideline, 2015). However, studies on the effects of planting season shifts on the dynamics of tobacco insect pests and diseases in the tobacco planting regions of Northern Vietnam remain fragmented and insufficiently synthesised, particularly under current climate change conditions. Therefore, synthesising and evaluating the effects of planting season shifts on pest and disease occurrence is essential for developing appropriate pest management strategies for those tobacco-growing regions.

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2. Materials and Methods

Meteorological data for the period 2020–2026 were collected from the Vietnam National Centre for Hydro-Meteorological Forecasting, including average temperature, rainfall, number of rainy days, and relative humidity during the tobacco growing seasons in the tobacco growing provinces of Northern Vietnam. Field survey data, insect pests and diseases investigation reports from the Vietnam Tobacco Institute during 2005–2026 were used to evaluate the effects of planting season shifts and low-temperature conditions on tobacco growth and the population dynamics of major insect pests and diseases.

In addition, scientific publications from both domestic and international sources were collected from Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science databases, and subsequently synthesised and analysed to assess the effects of growing season shifts on the dynamics of tobacco insect pests and diseases.

3. Weather Conditions and Tobacco Planting Seasons in Northern Vietnam

Planting season is one of the most important cultivation practices affecting the growth, yield, leaf quality, and the occurrence and severity of insect pests and diseases. Appropriate adjustment of planting time allows tobacco plants to grow under favourable weather conditions, thereby reducing the negative effects of adverse environmental factors and pest pressure during cultivation. Among the climatic factors influencing tobacco plants and harmful organisms, temperature, relative humidity, rainfall, number of rainy days, and light intensity are considered the most important environmental elements.

In recent years, the tobacco growing season in the provinces of Northern Vietnam has gradually shifted from the traditional planting season (February to early March) to earlier planting periods

(December to early January). This shift has considerably altered environmental conditions affecting tobacco growth as well as the occurrence and development of insect pests and diseases.

Figure 1. Major meteorological factors in Northern provinces of Vietnam during 2020–2026.

The traditional season generally provides favourable conditions for tobacco growth, with average temperatures of approximately 16–20°C during the transplanting stage and 20–24°C during the stalk, leaf growth stage (March–April). However, the harvesting and curing periods often coincide with the hot and rainy conditions from May to June, when average temperatures range from 26–28°C, maximum daily temperatures may reach 36–39°C, monthly rainfall ranges from 230–250 mm, and the number of rainy days reaches 15–16 days/month (Figure 1). Those weather conditions are unfavourable for leaf ripening, prolonging the ripening process, reducing leaf thickness and leaf weight, and causing difficulties during leaf curing (FAO, 2024).

In contrast, in the early season, tobacco grows in low temperatures, severe cold conditions, low rainfall, and drought stress. Those conditions suppress plant growth, restrict root development, reduce nutrient and water uptake, and prolong the growth duration in the field, thereby reducing tobacco yield and leaf quality. However, an advantage of early planting time is that harvesting and curing are concentrated during March–April, when weather conditions are drier, and rainfall is lower, contributing to a higher proportion of grade 1 and grade 2 of cured leaves. Observing meteorological data from 2020–2026 showed that the average temperature during December–April was approximately 15 - 23°C, while rainfall in December - April averaged about 6 - 77 mm. In contrast, both temperature and rainfall increased rapidly from May onward, with average values reaching 26°C and 250 mm in May, and 28°C and 240 mm in June.

Some studies have shown that tobacco plants grown under low-temperature conditions exhibit significant reductions in plant height, leaf number, stem diameter, leaf size, and overall plant morphology. According to Overstreet LF et al., 2008, low temperature severely reduced fresh leaf quality and directly affected curing characteristics, yield, and the quality of tobacco materials. Similarly, studies by Hu CM et al., 2008 and Li Y et al., 2021, cold conditions reduced root activity and nitrogen uptake from the soil, thereby seriously affecting carbon and nitrogen metabolism as well as dry matter accumulation in leaves. Din N-U et al., 2025, at temperatures below 16°C, dry matter accumulation decreased by 44.2% in the Huayan06 cultivar and by up to 66.4% in K326. Tobacco plants grow best at temperatures ranging from 22–24°C. When temperatures are below 16.5°C or exceed 30.5°C, plant growth and photosynthetic activity are significantly inhibited (Yang LY et al., 2017). In addition, temperatures below 18.5°C and above 28.5°C suppress leaf development and expansion. Similar responses have also been reported in tomato, cherry, and chicory plants, when temperatures below 16–18°C or above 35°C reduce leaf development and leaf area compared with optimal temperatures of 22–25°C (Mathieu AS et al., 2014).

Besides affecting growth, temperature also strongly influences plant development and senescence in tobacco. Low temperatures delayed flowering and senescence, whereas high temperatures accelerate plant development and ageing. Previous studies demonstrated that tobacco plants grown at 18.5°C flowered later and had a longer growth duration than those grown at 23.5°C. Similar findings were reported in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, when plants grown at 16°C exhibited delayed flowering compared with those grown at 23°C (Blázquez MA et al., 2003).

Overall, both domestic and international studies consistently indicate that low temperature and drought conditions negatively affect tobacco growth, development, and leaf quality. Slow tobacco growth under cold conditions may prolong the susceptible growth stage for viral diseases transmitted by insect vectors, thereby increasing disease incidence in the field. However, in Vietnam, there is still a lack of comprehensive studies evaluating the effects of early season, low temperature, and cold stress on tobacco growth, yield, quality, and pest and disease occurrence under the ecological conditions of the Northern provinces. Therefore, further studies on the effects of planting season and low-temperature conditions on tobacco are necessary to identify suitable planting periods, minimise adverse climatic impacts and pests, and improve tobacco production efficiency under current climate change conditions.

4. Effects of Planting Season Shifts on Tobacco insect Pests and Diseases

Planting season is a key agronomic factors affecting the occurrence, development, and damage potential of tobacco insect pests and diseases. A synthesis of survey data of the Vietnam Tobacco Institute during 2005–2026 showed that shifting the planting time from the traditional season to the early season considerably altered field ecological conditions, thereby strongly affecting the population dynamics of insect pests and viral diseases.

In general, early planting time tends to reduce the population density and damage incidence of several major insect pests in the field, including tobacco budworm, armyworm, tobacco aphid, and green stink bug. However, it also increases the risk of viral diseases transmitted by insect vectors. Among these, the tobacco aphid is an important vector of *Cucumber mosaic virus* (CMV) and *Potato virus Y* (PVY); thrips transmit *Tomato necrotic ringspot virus* (TNRV) and *Tomato spotted wilt virus* (TSWV); whereas whiteflies are vectors of *Tobacco leaf curl virus* (TLCV). Studies evaluating the effects of planting season shifts on the occurrence and development of tobacco insect pests and diseases in Vietnam remain limited and have not yet been comprehensively synthesised

Table 1. Effects of planting season on major insect pests and virus diseases in tobacco

Planting season	Main weather conditions	Major pests	Major virus diseases
Traditional season	Warm, humid	Budworm, aphid, armyworm	Low PVY incidence
Early season	Cold, dry	Reduced insect pressure	Increased PVY risk

4.1. Effects of Planting Season Shifts on Tobacco Insect Pests

The composition of insect pests varies across different growth stages of tobacco plants. Cutworms mainly damage newly transplanted seedlings, whereas tobacco budworm, tobacco aphid, and green stink bug commonly occur during the stalk and leaf development stage, and primarily damage young leaves. During the flowering stage and after topping, armyworm becomes the major pest affecting mature lower leaves. Entering the harvesting stage, armyworm infestation gradually declines.

Survey data of the Vietnam Tobacco Institute indicated that shifting the planting time to an earlier season considerably reduced the occurrence and damage levels of major insect pests. During 2005–2009, when transplanting was mainly conducted from February to early March, infestation rates of tobacco budworm, tobacco aphid, green stink bug, and armyworm were generally high, ranging from 9–36%, 6–30% (population density > 50 aphids per leaf), 13–17%, and 5–9%, respectively. In contrast, during 2023–2026, when planting in December, pest infestation levels decreased markedly, with infestation rates of tobacco budworm ranging from 0.2–2.8%, tobacco aphid: 0.2–2.3%, and armyworm: 0.1–2.0%, while green stink bug rarely occurred in the field. These findings indicate that

planting season plays an important role in regulating pest pressure in tobacco fields and may contribute to reducing the need for pesticide application.

Variations in pest occurrence between seasons are mainly associated with fluctuations in meteorological factors, particularly temperature and relative humidity. Under the traditional planting season, the stalk and leaf development stage usually occurs under temperatures of 20–23°C and relative humidity of 81–84%, which are favourable conditions for the development of many insect species. In contrast, under the early planting season, average temperatures are only approximately 15–16°C with lower relative humidity (RH: 77–80%). Those conditions reduce the growth and damaging activity of major insect pests.

Many studies worldwide have shown that most agricultural insect pests develop favourably under high temperatures and suitable humidity conditions. According to Wigglesworth, 1974, the optimal temperature range for most insects was approximately 20–35°C, whereas temperatures below 15°C markedly reduced flight activity, mating, and reproduction. Temperatures above 35°C could inhibit insect development or cause mortality due to dehydration (Robert E. Child, 2007).

For major tobacco insect pests, their favourable conditions for population development generally range from 20–30°C with relative humidity of 80–90%. For tobacco budworm, it can develop within temperatures ranging from 13.3–33°C and RH 50–90%, with optimal conditions of 21–24°C and RH 80–85%. When temperatures are below 13.3°C or exceed 33°C, budworm activity is considerably restricted. Under conditions of 20–21°C combined with RH \leq 65%, mortality of newly hatched larvae may reach 96.15%, and most pupae fail to emerge due to unsuccessful moulting. At temperatures above 29–30°C combined with RH 80–81%, larval mortality may reach 82–83% (Nguyen Van Chin, 2021). Similarly, Mironidis et al., 2012 reported that tobacco budworm entered diapause at temperatures below 15°C and could die under extremely low thermal thresholds, whereas Phillips et al., 1966 suggested that pupae could remain in diapause for up to 20 months at temperatures below 18°C. In addition, fecundity decreases sharply at temperatures below 20°C, particularly below 15°C (Noor-ul-Ane et al., 2018).

Similar to tobacco budworm, tobacco aphid also develops rapidly under warm and proper humidity conditions. Previous studies demonstrated that aphid populations can develop at temperatures ranging from 4.9–32°C and RH 60–100%, with optimal conditions around 20–25°C and RH 80–85%. When temperatures fall below 17°C or exceed 30°C with RH below 70%, aphid activity decreases substantially. At temperatures below 4.9°C or above 32°C combined with RH below 60%, aphid activity is almost completely suppressed in the field. Other studies also indicated that aphid populations develop favourably at 20–25°C with RH 75–88% (Tiwari et al., 2018), and population density often peaks at 20–22°C (Narjary et al., 2013). When temperatures are below 17°C, the intrinsic rate of population increase declines markedly (Baral S. et al., 2022). Furthermore, aphids are unable to fly at temperatures below 13–16°C (Irwin et al., 2007), and the development rate of the pre-reproductive stage decreases substantially at temperatures \leq 15°C (Duffy et al., 2017).

Overall, previous studies consistently demonstrated that shifting the planting season to earlier periods creates cooler and drier conditions during the stalk and leaf development stage, thereby significantly reducing the occurrence and damage potential of both sap-sucking and leaf-feeding insect pests. Adjustment of planting season can therefore be considered an important ecological approach in integrated pest management (IPM) for tobacco production in the Northern mountainous provinces of Vietnam. However, excessively early planting may negatively affect tobacco growth, yield, and leaf quality due to prolonged low-temperature and drought stress conditions. In addition, slow plant growth under cold conditions may prolong the susceptible growth stage for insect vector-transmitted viral diseases. Therefore, further comprehensive studies are needed to identify optimal planting periods that simultaneously minimise pest occurrence while maintaining tobacco yield and raw material quality under the ecological conditions of Northern Vietnam.

4.2. Effects of planting season shifts on virus diseases transmitted by insect vectors

In recent years, the shift in tobacco planting seasons from the traditional season to earlier planting periods has considerably altered field ecological conditions in the northern mountainous provinces of

Vietnam. These changes have not only affected tobacco growth and development but also significantly influenced the composition, population dynamics, and severity of virus diseases transmitted by insect vectors. Virus diseases recorded in tobacco fields include *Tobacco leaf curl virus* (TLCV), *Cucumber mosaic virus* (CMV), *Tomato spotted wilt virus* (TSWV), *Tobacco necrotic ring virus* (TNRV), and *Potato virus Y* (PVY). Among them, PVY has been identified as the most economically important virus affecting tobacco raw material production in Northern Vietnam.

Survey data compiled by the Vietnam Tobacco Institute showed that under the traditional planting season, CMV and TLCV were the predominant viruses in the field, with low disease incidence of less than 0.5%. However, when planting dates were shifted earlier, both the composition and incidence of virus diseases increased markedly. During 2020–2023, three major viruses were commonly recorded, including CMV, TLCV, and PVY, with disease incidence ranging from 0.1–1.9%, 0.1–1.3%, and 0.1–16.5%, respectively. During 2024–2026, five virus species were detected in tobacco fields, including CMV (0.3–5.5%), TLCV (0.5–5.8%), TSWV (0.2–1.6%), TNRV (0.1–3.0%), and PVY (1.8–22.1%). Severe outbreaks were observed in excessively early-planted fields established in early November. In Bac Son District, Lạng Sơn, TLCV incidence reached 30–90%, while in Cao Bang, CMV incidence ranged from 5–15%. Among all recorded viruses, PVY was the most widespread and destructive virus disease in tobacco-growing provinces of Northern Vietnam.

The occurrence and spread of PVY were closely associated with the population dynamics of aphid vectors, particularly winged aphids. Field surveys conducted in northern tobacco-growing provinces showed that prior to severe PVY outbreaks, populations of winged adult aphids increased markedly in tobacco fields (Figure 2). Specifically, in Bac Son District, Lạng Sơn, winged aphid populations increased rapidly from January to February before severe PVY outbreaks occurred in March. Similarly, in Chi Lang District, Lạng Sơn, winged aphids were commonly observed from February to early March, whereas severe PVY incidence developed from March to early April. Tobacco fields planted excessively early or intercropped with winter tobacco crops in Bac Son District frequently exhibited high PVY incidence ranging from 30–100%.

Under prolonged cold conditions, the survival period and dispersal activity of winged aphids increase, creating favourable conditions for virus transmission between tobacco plants and in fields. In contrast, under warmer conditions, apterous aphid populations become dominant, and PVY incidence decreases considerably. These findings are consistent with previous studies demonstrating that winged aphids play a critical role in PVY transmission through a non-persistent transmission mechanism (Broadbent, 1948; Watson and Roberts, 1939).

Figure 2. Dynamics of winged aphids and PVY incidence in Northern Vietnam in 2025

Survey data on the effects of planting seasons on PVY incidence in the northern provinces of Vietnam were consistent with field experiments conducted in Bac Giang Province during 2017 and 2018. Tobacco planted in the early season showed the highest PVY incidence and severity, resulting in

substantial reductions in tobacco yield and quality, whereas late-planted tobacco exhibited the lowest disease levels. In 2017, early-planted tobacco (January 5) had 100% disease incidence and a disease index of 90.1%, with yield reductions of 68.2% and 61.8% compared with the late and main seasons, respectively. Tobacco planted during the main season (February 8) showed disease incidence of approximately 67.8% and a disease index of 56.4%, with yield reduced by 16.9% compared with the late season. In contrast, late-planted tobacco (February 28) had disease incidence of only 21.5% and a disease index of 13.5%, with yields reaching 22.3 t ha⁻¹. Similar trends were observed in 2018, when early-planted tobacco exhibited the highest disease incidence (66.1%) and disease index (40.7%), whereas late-planted tobacco had considerably lower disease incidence (19.5%) and disease index (5.9%). Yield in the late season was more than 50% higher than that of the early season.

Regarding disease development, PVY incidence gradually increased after transplanting and reached peak severity approximately 100 days after planting in the early season, compared with 60 days in the main season and 50 days in the late season. These findings indicate that prolonged tobacco growth duration in the field increases PVY incidence and disease severity. However, the progression of PVY symptoms in the early season was slower than that observed in the main and late seasons (Nguyen Van Chin et al., 2018).

One of the major causes is that early-planted tobacco is exposed for a prolonged period to low-temperature and drought conditions, which suppress plant growth, delay flowering, restrict root development, and reduce water and nutrient uptake. These adverse conditions weaken plant resistance to virus infection and replication compared with tobacco grown in the main and late seasons. Moreover, the extended growth period increases the duration of exposure to both virus sources and insect vectors, thereby increasing the risk of virus infection in the field.

In addition to host plant effects, prolonged cold and dry conditions also alter aphid populations in tobacco fields. Under low-temperature conditions, winged adult aphids survive longer, whereas under warmer conditions, wingless aphid populations become dominant. Because winged aphids can move more easily among plants and between tobacco fields, their virus transmission efficiency is substantially greater than that of wingless aphids, which are generally more localised and less mobile. Therefore, climatic changes associated with early planting simultaneously affect tobacco growth, vector population dynamics, and the development of insect-transmitted virus diseases.

Previous studies have shown that PVY belongs to the genus *Potyvirus* and is transmitted primarily by the green peach aphid (*Myzus persicae*) (Hull, 2002; Radcliffe, 1982). However, only winged aphids are capable of transmitting the virus horizontally from infected plants to healthy plants because virus retention and transmission ability persist only for a short period (Broadbent, 1948) through a non-persistent transmission mechanism (Watson and Roberts, 1939). Therefore, the timing of appearance, population density, and dispersal behaviour of winged aphids play decisive roles in the spread of PVY in tobacco fields (Robert et al., 2000).

In addition to virus vectors, host plant susceptibility is also an important factor affecting PVY development. Mature plants generally exhibit greater disease tolerance than young or weak plants due to the presence of physical barriers, such as trichomes and epicuticular wax layers, which can reduce feeding and infestation by piercing-sucking insects, thereby limiting virus entry into plant tissues. Disease resistance may also be associated with the release of volatile compounds that repel insect vectors or with stronger intrinsic antiviral defence systems capable of suppressing virus replication after transmission into the host plant (Chung et al., 2015; Fajinmi and Fajinmi, 2010). Furthermore, in mature plants, virus movement into fully developed tissues occurs more slowly or may even be completely restricted because viruses move through the phloem following a source-to-sink transport pathway (Roberts et al., 1997). In contrast, in young and actively growing plants, viruses can spread rapidly into developing tissues, resulting in severe disease symptoms within a short period. Temperature is considered one of the most important environmental factors influencing interactions between host plants and RNA viruses. Low temperatures suppress plant growth and reduce plant resistance to virus infection, replication, and systemic movement within host tissues. High temperatures can enhance antiviral defence mechanisms mediated by gene silencing (Del Toro et al.,

2015, Chellappan et al., 2005, Szittyta et al., 2003), whereas hypersensitive resistance against PVY in potato is more effective under low-temperature conditions (Valkonen, 1997). Kyung San Choi et al., 2017 demonstrated that temperature strongly affected the timing and incidence of systemic PVY infection in upper leaves. No systemic infection was observed at 12°C, 16°C, or 35°C at 17 days after inoculation. The time required for systemic infection decreased as temperature increased, from 14.0 days at 20°C to 5.7 days at 28°C, and then increased again at higher temperatures. The proportion of plants showing systemic infection reached 100% at 24°C and 28°C but declined to 90% at 32°C and only 20% at 20°C. The lower thermal threshold for systemic infection was estimated at 15.6°C, and the thermal requirement for systemic PVY infection was determined to be 65.6 degree-days (DD). Disease incidence increased gradually between 16°C and 35°C, reached a maximum at 28°C, and declined at higher temperatures. These findings suggest that under low-temperature conditions below 20°C, tobacco plants infected with PVY could develop only localised infections rather than systemic infections. This information is highly important for forecasting and managing PVY in tobacco-growing provinces of Northern Vietnam.

Studies on virus acquisition and transmission by aphids have shown that these processes are strongly influenced by environmental factors, particularly temperature and relative humidity. According to Chung et al. 2016, the efficiency of PVY acquisition and transmission by aphids increased progressively between 10°C and 30°C and reached its optimum at approximately 20°C. When temperatures exceeded 20°C, both virus acquisition and transmission efficiency gradually declined, with the sharpest reduction observed above 25°C. These findings indicate that PVY develops and spreads most effectively under temperatures ranging from 15–20°C. Similarly, Marcin Przybyś et al., 2017 reported that when average daily temperatures exceeded 25°C, the risk of PVY infection decreased by approximately 24%. This reduction was attributed to lower virus concentrations within plant cells and reduced symptom expression on leaves at higher temperatures. The optimal temperature range for replication and symptom expression of PVY^N was reported to be 22–26°C, whereas for PVY^O the optimum range was 14–22°C (De Bokx et al., 1997). The efficiency of virus acquisition and transmission also depends on the temperature at which aphids feed on infected plants and must occur within an optimal thermal range. Transmission efficiency of the PVY^O strain is highest at 20°C. Kyung San Choi et al., 2017, further demonstrated that the proportion of potato plants showing systemic infection declined to only 20% at 20°C, whereas 100% systemic infection occurred at 24°C and 28°C. The completion rate of systemic infection decreased sharply at temperatures below 16°C. This may be explained by slower virus replication rates, the inability of the virus to overcome plant defence responses, or restricted systemic movement of the virus after infection.

In addition to temperature, relative humidity also significantly affects aphid-mediated virus transmission. Singh et al., 1988 reported that relative humidity of approximately 80% provided favourable conditions for PVY development and spread, whereas transmission efficiency declined by nearly 50% at 50% relative humidity. High humidity before and after inoculation also increased host plant susceptibility to infection. These findings indicate that PVY occurrence and spread are strongly dependent on the interactions among climatic conditions, vector activity, and the physiological status of host plants.

Field surveys and previous studies indicate that early planting alters interactions among host plants, vector populations, and climatic conditions, thereby increasing the risk of PVY outbreaks in Northern Vietnam. In particular, the timing of aphid appearance, population density, and dispersal intensity, especially of winged aphids, are identified as the major factors determining PVY outbreaks and transmission in tobacco fields, providing important information for disease forecasting and management.

From the host plant perspective, tobacco grown during the early season develops under prolonged low-temperature and dry conditions, resulting in slower growth, weaker plants, and reduced resistance to virus diseases. These conditions also prolong the stalk and leaf growth stage, thereby extending the exposure period of tobacco plants to virus sources and insect vectors, which consequently increases disease incidence and severity in the field. Field observations further indicated that the most susceptible growth stage of tobacco to PVY extends from transplanting until flowering. After

flowering and topping, disease severity decreased markedly, suggesting that plant ageing is associated with reduced susceptibility to virus infection and restricted virus movement within host tissues. In other words, greater physiological maturity increases plant tolerance to virus invasion and systemic movement within tobacco plants. In addition to factors such as residual inoculum sources in the field and the use of susceptible tobacco cultivars, the specific ecological conditions associated with early planting create favourable conditions for PVY development. This explains why early-planted tobacco generally shows a higher risk of PVY infection than tobacco grown during the traditional planting season.

Besides host susceptibility, early planting also modifies interactions among host plants, vector populations, and climatic conditions, thereby increasing the risk of PVY outbreaks and spread in northern tobacco-growing regions of Vietnam. The timing of aphid occurrence, population density, and dispersal patterns, particularly those of winged aphids, play decisive roles in PVY epidemics in the field. The period of greatest susceptibility to PVY extends from transplanting until flowering, whereas disease severity declines substantially after flowering and topping due to age-related reductions in plant susceptibility to virus infection. Therefore, the ecological conditions associated with early planting are considered a major factor promoting PVY occurrence, spread, and damage in tobacco fields.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework illustrating the ecological effects of early planting on PVY transmission in tobacco fields.

Field investigations conducted in northern mountainous provinces showed that local tobacco cultivars possess greater tolerance to cold and drought stress than newly introduced cultivars and are therefore commonly used for early planting. However, these local cultivars are generally more susceptible to virus diseases, particularly PVY. During the early season, climatic conditions are relatively favourable for both PVY transmission and vector development, with average temperatures ranging from 15–20.4°C and relative humidity ranging from 77–84% between December and March. The shift toward earlier planting has promoted earlier development and field occurrence of aphid populations, especially winged aphids, from December to February, thereby increasing virus incidence during 2025, particularly in Bac Son District, Lang Son province. These findings are consistent with previous studies reported by Jeger et al., 2018 and Korbecka-Glinka, 2021.

5. Management Strategies for Tobacco Pests and Diseases Related to Planting Season

Recent studies indicated that the management of vector-borne virus diseases in tobacco requires an integrated approach because disease outbreaks are closely associated with planting season, environmental conditions, vector dynamics, and host susceptibility. Among these diseases, Potato virus Y (PVY) is considered one of the most destructive viral pathogens affecting tobacco production in Northern Vietnam. Therefore, integrated pest management (IPM) strategies have been increasingly applied to minimise disease incidence and reduce economic losses.

Based on field investigations and long-term monitoring in the tobacco-growing provinces of Northern Vietnam, several management practices have been recommended, including adjustment of planting season, removal of virus inoculum sources, deployment of resistant cultivars, management of aphid vectors, and rational pesticide use. These integrated measures have contributed to reducing virus transmission and improving tobacco yield and leaf quality under changing climatic conditions.

5.1. Management of Inoculum Sources and Alternative Hosts

Overwintering inoculum sources and alternative host plants play important roles in the occurrence and spread of tobacco virus diseases. Therefore, field sanitation, destruction of infected plant residues, and removal of virus host plants and insect vector hosts before and after the growing season are essential measures to reduce primary inoculum pressure. Previous studies demonstrated that the continuous presence of host and alternative host plants considerably increases the risk of virus transmission in subsequent cropping seasons.

5.2. Crop Rotation and Adjustment of Planting Season

Crop rotation with non-host crops, particularly paddy rice, contributes to disrupting vector life cycles and reducing virus inoculum sources in the field. In contrast, continuous tobacco cultivation or overlapping tobacco cropping seasons may increase the accumulation of virus inoculum and insect vectors, thereby facilitating virus transmission from winter tobacco crops to spring crops.

Adjustment of planting season is considered one of the most important ecological approaches for virus disease management. The present review indicates that excessively early planting under prolonged low-temperature and drought conditions increases the risk of PVY and TLCV outbreaks because tobacco plants remain longer in the vegetative growth stage and are exposed to virus vectors for extended periods. Conversely, excessively late planting may increase insect pest pressure and negatively affect cured leaf quality. Under the ecological conditions of Northern mountainous Vietnam, transplanting from late January to mid-February appears to be more suitable for balancing tobacco growth performance and pest and disease risks.

5.3. Use of Resistant Cultivars and Virus-Free Seedlings

The use of virus-resistant or virus-tolerant cultivars is an important strategy for reducing disease severity in tobacco fields. Several tobacco cultivars, including D61, GL7, GL9, and GL10, showed better resistance to virus diseases than commonly cultivated local cultivars. However, local cultivars are still widely grown in many production areas because of their better adaptation to low-temperature and drought conditions, although these cultivars are generally more susceptible to major tobacco virus diseases.

In addition, the production of virus-free seedlings during the nursery stage plays an important role in minimising primary inoculum sources before transplanting to the field.

5.4. Management of Virus Vectors

Early control of insect vectors, particularly winged aphids, is considered a key strategy for managing non-persistently transmitted viruses such as PVY. Field surveys in Northern Vietnam indicated that winged adult aphids usually appear shortly after tobacco establishment and early vegetative growth in the field. Therefore, regular monitoring of vector populations during the 3–16 leaf stage is important for forecasting disease outbreaks and supporting timely management decisions.

In areas with frequent virus outbreaks, integrated vector management combined with the application of resistance inducers or antiviral agents may considerably reduce disease incidence. However, pesticide applications should follow recommended guidelines and involve rotation of active ingredients to minimise the risk of insecticide resistance development in vector populations.

5.5. Effectiveness of Integrated Management Strategies

Field application of integrated management practices in Northern Vietnam demonstrated that the incidence of virus diseases, particularly PVY, has markedly decreased in recent years. During 2014–2017, severe PVY outbreaks were frequently recorded in Bac Son and Chi Lang districts (Lang Son Province), where disease incidence exceeded 30% in many tobacco fields. However, after the implementation of integrated management strategies, disease incidence in most tobacco-growing areas during 2021–2022 declined to below 1%.

Overall, both research findings and field observations indicate that the management of insect vector-borne virus diseases in tobacco should be conducted based on ecological and integrated management approaches. Among the available measures, appropriate adjustment of planting season combined with inoculum source management, deployment of resistant cultivars, and effective vector control plays a critical role in reducing the occurrence and spread of virus diseases in the tobacco-growing provinces of Northern Vietnam.

6. Conclusion

The shift in planting season from the traditional season to earlier planting periods in the mountainous provinces of Northern Vietnam has substantially altered field ecological conditions, thereby affecting tobacco growth and the occurrence of insect pests and diseases. Early planting time reduces the incidence of several major insect pests, including tobacco budworm, armyworm, tobacco aphid, and green stink bug, due to lower temperatures and drier conditions during the stalk and leaf growth stage. However, prolonged cold and drought conditions increase the risk of insect vector-borne virus diseases, particularly Potato virus Y (PVY), because tobacco plants develop more slowly, remain susceptible for longer periods, and are exposed to increased dispersal of winged aphids in the field.

The present review indicates that adjustment of planting season is an important ecological approach in integrated pest management (IPM) for tobacco production. Planting during January tends to suppress major insect pests, whereas transplanting from late January to mid-February contributes to reducing the risk of vector-borne virus diseases while maintaining tobacco yield and cured leaf quality.

Nevertheless, further studies are still required to determine the most suitable planting periods for different ecological regions in order to balance tobacco productivity, leaf quality, and pest and disease management under current climate change conditions.

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